

An open modeling framework to support the electrification of private transport in African cities: A case study of Addis Ababa[☆]

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ABSTRACT

The electrification of road transport, as the predominant mode of transportation in Africa, represents a great opportunity to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and dependence on costly fuel imports. However, it introduces major challenges for local energy infrastructures, including the deployment of charging stations and the impact on fragile electricity grids. Existing planning tools often depend on detailed mobility data that is unavailable in many African contexts, especially for privately owned passenger vehicles. To address this gap, we introduce a novel and open framework designed to support the electrification of private vehicles in data-scarce regions. We apply our approach to a case study of Addis Ababa, where we model the introduction of 100,000 electric vehicles, simulating their daily mobility patterns and charging needs. Our analysis estimates a daily charging demand of approximately 350 MWh and underscores the importance of the charging location on the spatial and temporal distribution of this demand. Notably, charging at public places can help smooth the charging demand throughout the day, mitigating peak charging loads on the electricity grid. We also estimate charging station requirements, finding that workplace charging requires approximately one charging point per three electric vehicles, while public charging requires only one per thirty. Finally, we demonstrate that photovoltaic energy can cover a substantial share of the charging needs, emphasizing the potential for renewable energy integration. Demonstrated through its application in Addis Ababa, this study provides a transferable framework for electric vehicle planning in other data-scarce cities.

1. Introduction

Africa's road-dependent transport sector is rapidly expanding (United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP), 2021; Network of African Science Academies (NASAC), InterAcademy Partnership (IAP), 2024), with demand for transport fuels projected to increase by two-thirds by 2040 under current policies (United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP), 2021). This growing reliance on fossil fuels presents critical economic and environmental challenges, particularly as many African nations strive to meet their climate commitments under the Paris Agreement. In response, several governments are setting targets and policies to promote low-emission mobility solutions, recognizing the need to shift away from conventional fossil fuel-based transport

systems (Addis Ababa Institute of Technology (AAIT), 2021; Ayetor et al., 2023). In this context, electric vehicles (EVs) are emerging as a promising solution, especially given the continent's vast renewable energy potential. EV adoption could also deliver economic benefits by reducing the dependence on costly fuel imports and mitigating associated foreign exchange (forex) risks, playing a key role in advancing both climate and economic sustainability across the continent. However, the large-scale deployment of EVs introduces complex planning challenges, including how to determine the optimal charging infrastructure and mitigate grid impacts. Even a modest increase in private EV adoption has the potential to impose considerable stress on local power grids (Mudaheranwa et al., 2023). Thus, there is a need

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for electric mobility planning tools and studies that can support the transition to EVs in Africa, taking into account the continent's diverse energy and mobility landscapes.

Addis Ababa – the capital of Ethiopia – offers a compelling case study for exploring the electrification of privately owned vehicles. The city stands out not only for its political and economic importance but also for symbolizing a dual narrative of transformative opportunities and critical challenges. On the one hand, Ethiopia became the first country to implement a total ban on the import of fossil fuel private automobiles, a policy in place since January 2024 (Climate Policy Database, 2024; Le Monde, 2024). In line with this ambitious policy, the government has introduced financial incentives to promote EVs, including import tax reductions and exemptions from VAT, excise, and surtaxes (Addis Ababa Institute of Technology (AAIT), 2021; Eticha and Emagnu, 2023; Ministry of Transport and Logistics (MoTL), 2022). Over the next decade, the country aims to import several hundred thousand EVs (Addis Ababa Institute of Technology (AAIT), 2021). As of 2020, Addis Ababa was home to more than half of Ethiopia's 1.2 million registered vehicles (Eticha and Emagnu, 2023). Consequently, the city is expected to absorb the majority of future electric vehicle imports. On the other hand, there are concerns about whether local energy infrastructures can support the large-scale adoption of EVs. Currently, Addis Ababa has only a handful of public charging stations (Electromaps, 2024), and the rapid expansion of home charging facilities may further strain Addis Ababa's power system, which already faces frequent electricity supply interruptions (Tsegai, 2022; Meles, 2020). As shown in Fig. 1, the grid undergoes high electricity demand fluctuations. During peak periods, Ethiopia's overloaded and aging distribution network struggles to accommodate demand spikes (Agajie et al., 2024). On the supply side, this challenge is compounded by the country's reliance on hydropower (Gebremeskel et al., 2023; International Energy Agency (IEA), 2023), which makes the system vulnerable to rainfall variability, a risk that is expected to increase over the long term due to climate change (Wheeler et al., 2020; Kemarau et al., 2025). Studies are therefore urgently needed to guide policies and strategic infrastructure planning, ensuring that Ethiopia's ambitious electrification efforts translate into a smooth and sustainable transition. However, the lack of suitable data and tailored tools poses an important challenge to achieving this goal.

In this study, we propose a novel open-source modeling framework to support EV planning, and we demonstrate its application in the case of Addis Ababa. The framework leverages open geospatial data to estimate EV charging needs and their spatio-temporal distribution. Based on these estimates, the implications for charging infrastructure requirements and the potential contribution of photovoltaic (PV) energy in meeting the charging needs are also quantified. To our knowledge, no comparable end-to-end framework has been developed for data-scarce regions like Addis Ababa, where existing approaches are typically designed for high-income contexts and rely on extensive mobility data. Our work therefore makes an important contribution by providing a generalizable framework to support EV planning in African cities. By applying this framework to Addis Ababa, we also address three interrelated research questions that are central to the city's EV transition:

- What is the additional electricity demand from private passenger EV charging, and how is it distributed spatially and temporally, considering different charging locations?
- What are the implications for Addis Ababa in terms of charging infrastructure requirements?
- How can locally installed PV systems contribute to meeting this additional demand?

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows. Section 2 reviews existing literature on EV planning frameworks and identifies key research gaps. Section 3 introduces the proposed modeling framework. Section 4 demonstrates its application to Addis Ababa, providing

Fig. 1. Hourly electricity demand profile for Addis Ababa on a typical weekday, derived from national demand data provided by the National Grid Control Center and scaled to the city level. The scaling methodology is detailed in Appendix E.

insights into the local context and the crucial factors for EV planning studies. Section 5 presents the results and discussion, while Section 6 concludes the study and highlights directions for future research. This work not only provides critical insights into the infrastructure planning needs for Addis Ababa but also offers a transferable methodology for electric mobility planning in other cities.

2. Literature review

A growing body of literature has focused on developing models and methods to support EV planning, with several comprehensive reviews available (Hu et al., 2021; Andrenacci and Valentini, 2023; Lin et al., 2024; Shariatzadeh et al., 2025). Within this literature, frameworks designed for local planning are required to simulate the EV demand with sufficient spatial and temporal resolution. Following Daina, Sivakumar, and Polack (Daina et al., 2017), two categories of models are particularly relevant in this context: “Direct Use of Observed Activity-Travel Schedules” (DUOATS) and “Activity-Based Models” (ABM). As the name suggests, both approaches rely on so-called activity-travel schedules (Pareschi et al., 2020), but differ in how these schedules are obtained.

In DUOATS models (Daina et al., 2017; Pareschi et al., 2020), activity-travel schedules are used directly as exogenous inputs, typically derived from detailed household travel surveys within the study area. This approach therefore depends heavily on the availability and quality of such surveys, which remain limited in low- and middle-income countries despite ongoing efforts to bridge this data gap (Demissie et al., 2016; Blanchard et al., 2023). By contrast, activity-based models (ABMs) (Nguyen et al., 2025) generate schedules endogenously, often within agent-based frameworks such as MATSim (Horni et al., 2016) which has emerged as the open-source benchmark for simulating EV demand (Adenaw and Lienkamp, 2021). Several derivatives of MATSim, such as UrbanEV (Adenaw and Lienkamp, 2021) and BEAM (Sheppard et al., 2017), have also developed specifically to model electric vehicles. In ABMs, EV agents dynamically decide when and where to charge based on predefined behavioral rules, enabling, in principle, a realistic bottom-up representation of travel patterns. However, these models require complex workflows with numerous behavioral parameters (Sheppard et al., 2017; Bastariento et al., 2023), and default parameterizations are generally calibrated in high-income contexts, limiting their transferability (Bwambale et al., 2019). The complexity of such models also introduces concerns in terms of computational resources (Bastariento et al., 2023).

Furthermore, existing approaches focus only on estimating the charging demand, without addressing charging infrastructure needs or the potential contribution of renewable energy sources such as PV systems. For example, while MATSim-based frameworks are capable of generating high-resolution charging demand, they lack direct integration of PV production (Adenaw and Lienkamp, 2021; Sheppard et al., 2017). Similarly, charging infrastructure planning is often addressed through optimization-based methods, but these approaches mainly remain confined to research code or standalone tools (Li et al., 2024). The absence of end-to-end modeling frameworks that integrate demand, supply, and charging infrastructure underscores the need for tools that extend beyond demand quantification to offer actionable insights for the effective deployment of electric vehicles.

In the African context, studies and the development of tailored modeling tools to support EV planning remain at an early stage. Our literature review indicates that most efforts have focused on public transport systems (Collett et al., 2021; Rix et al., 2022; Giliomee et al., 2023, 2024), leaving private vehicle adoption largely underexplored. Given the growth of private car ownership in some African cities such as Addis Ababa, this segment will play a critical role in shaping the future charging demand. While some studies have investigated specific strategies like vehicle-to-grid (V2G) solutions (McPherson et al., 2018; Bouguerra and Bhar Layeb, 2019) or coordinated EV charging to mitigate peak electricity demand (Dioha et al., 2022; Makeen et al., 2023), these analyses do not consider the spatial and temporal distribution of the charging demand. Crucially, to the best of our knowledge, these studies have not resulted in the development or demonstration of an end-to-end, open-source modeling framework capable of addressing the challenges of data-scarce regions.

Overall, the literature review reveals three key gaps. First, existing EV demand models are complex and data-intensive, limiting their applicability across different contexts. Second, most tools analyze charging demand in isolation, providing limited insight into infrastructure needs or renewable energy integration. Third, in the African context, research has predominantly focused on public transport, leaving the planning of private vehicle electrification underexplored. This study addresses these gaps by developing and demonstrating an open-source framework that integrates EV demand modeling, charging infrastructure, and photovoltaic energy supply — explicitly designed for data-scarce regions.

3. Methodology

The proposed model provides a comprehensive and integrated framework to analyze passenger mobility demand, EV charging needs, the potential of PV energy to meet these needs, and the required charging infrastructure across various charging locations. By providing detailed modeling of intra-urban mobility patterns, the model is particularly well-suited for supporting electric mobility planning in cities. As illustrated in Fig. 2, the framework is structured around three main steps:

1. **Mobility demand:** This step simulates daily mobility patterns with a specific focus on detailed spatial modeling of home-to-work commuting flows through the use of geospatial data.
2. **Charging demand:** The model then determines the spatio-temporal distribution of EV charging needs and estimates the required number of charging points. It relies on EV fleet properties, defined for each vehicle type (battery capacity, energy consumption per kilometer, and maximum charging power), as well as user charging habits (share of EVs charging at home, work and public places) and charging infrastructure properties (available charging power at each location).
3. **EV-PV complementarity:** Finally, the complementarity between local PV production and EVs is assessed. Using basic parameters of local PV installations, the model evaluates how effectively PV energy can fulfill EV charging needs.

Designed to be flexible and operable with open-source geospatial data, the framework is particularly well suited for regions with limited data availability or uncertain development trajectories, making it a versatile tool for strategic decision-making in various contexts. The following sections provide a detailed description of each modeling step.

3.1. Mobility demand

The first step involves quantifying the daily mobility demand of electric vehicles using a spatially-dependent mobility modeling approach. This process involves dividing the study area into smaller, manageable units, referred to as traffic zones (TZs). A certain number of EVs is then allocated to each TZ relative to its population, and a trip distribution model is applied to simulate vehicle flows and travel distances between zones.

The model primarily focuses on capturing weekday mobility patterns, with a particular emphasis on home-to-work commuting and the associated charging needs at home, work, and public charging locations. Home-to-work trips are expected to dominate the weekday mobility demand (Eurostat, 2021), justifying their central role in the modeling framework. However, to ensure applicability across various case studies, the model also allows for the incorporation of an additional travel distance for other trip purposes such as shopping trips or recreational trips.

3.1.1. Zoning

The zoning process divides the study area into traffic zones using a regular square scheme (Ghadiri et al., 2019), where each TZ is equal in size and shape, ensuring simplicity and uniform spatial granularity. This zoning scheme also facilitates seamless integration with the self-calibrating trip distribution model introduced in Section 3.1.3. To generate the TZs, the study area is automatically subdivided into a grid of equal-sized zones, with each zone's size determined to be as close as possible to a target size specified as an input parameter. Each zone is assigned a unique identifier, and geospatial data are aggregated at the zone level, including residential population, number of workplaces, and number of points of interest (POIs).

3.1.2. Vehicle allocation

Following the zoning process, the next step involves populating the different zones with the number of EVs to be simulated. This vehicle allocation step is based on residential population, assuming that the number of vehicles n_i of a traffic zone i is proportional to the number of people P_i of that zone

$$n_i = \frac{P_i}{P_{tot}} \cdot n_{tot} \quad (1)$$

where P_{tot} is the total population across all zones and n_{tot} the total number of simulated EVs. The resulting number of EVs per zone, n_i , is rounded to the nearest integer, while ensuring that the total allocated vehicles matches the target number n_{tot} . Note that our framework allows for refining this allocation if real vehicle ownership statistics are available. In this work, due to the lack of such detailed data, we rely on population-based allocation.

3.1.3. Trip distribution

The vehicle flows for home-to-work trips between TZs are estimated using a production-constrained spatial interaction model (Fotheringham, 2001), based on a gravity law with a decaying exponential function. Given the number of vehicles commuting from a specific traffic zone (origin), the model calculates the number of trips directed towards other zones (destinations) by assuming that the number of trips between two zones is proportional to the so-called attractiveness of the destination (equal to the number of workplaces) and decays with distance, following an exponential law. This approach was selected because it has been shown to outperform other models for trip distribution, particularly at small spatial scales (Liang et al., 2013; Lenormand

Fig. 2. Overview of the three main steps of the modeling framework.

et al., 2016). Numerically, the trip distribution model calculates the probability p_{ij} that a vehicle originating from zone i travels to zone j as

$$p_{ij} = c_i \cdot A_j \cdot \exp(-\beta \cdot d_{ij}) \quad (2)$$

where A_j is the attractiveness of zone j (measured by the number of workplaces), d_{ij} is the inter-zone distance in km, β is a free parameter in km^{-1} , and c_i is a normalization constant ensuring that the probabilities for all possible destinations sum to 1.

Importantly, the parameter β is determined using a self-calibrating approach, which eliminates the need for manual calibration of the trip distribution model, an essential feature for regions where detailed mobility data is unavailable. Based on the extensive work of Lenormand et al. (2016), β is defined as:

$$\beta = 0.3 \cdot S^{-0.18} \quad (3)$$

where S represents the surface area of the traffic zones in km^2 . This formulation was validated by Lenormand et al. (2016) across a wide range of contexts (including Europe, North America, and South America), highlighting a form of universality in commuting mobility patterns, as also observed in other studies (Yan et al., 2014, 2017). As such, it provides a robust and transferable baseline for data-scarce regions. Nevertheless, if local data is available such as the average commuting distance, our framework allows for further calibration of β to better reflect local conditions.

3.2. Charging demand

The spatial and temporal estimation of the EV charging demand is performed in two modeling steps, each using a distinct methodology. First, the daily charging demand is calculated for each traffic zone and charging location category (home, work, and POIs). Second, a stochastic modeling approach is used to determine the temporal charging demand, accounting for the variability in the EV charging load profiles.

3.2.1. Spatial demand

The spatial charging demand for a given traffic zone i is segmented by charging location: at home ($E_{home,i}$ [kWh]), at work ($E_{work,i}$ [kWh]), and at POIs ($E_{POI,i}$ [kWh]). The total demand is the sum of these components. The formulation, developed in this study and presented below, differs slightly in its calculation for home and work locations compared to POIs.

For home and work, the charging demand is calculated as the product of the vehicle kilometers (VKM [km]) derived from the mobility demand model, the corresponding charging location shares (f_{home} and f_{work}), the average energy consumption per kilometer of EVs (C_{EV} [kWh/km]), and the inverse of the charging efficiency (η_{charge}):

$$E_{home,i} = f_{home} \cdot C_{EV} \cdot \eta_{charge}^{-1} \cdot VKM_{out,i} \quad (4)$$

$$E_{work,i} = f_{work} \cdot C_{EV} \cdot \eta_{charge}^{-1} \cdot VKM_{in,i} \quad (5)$$

Here, $VKM_{out,i}$ represents the distance traveled by vehicles from traffic zone i to other zones, while $VKM_{in,i}$ refers to the distance traveled by vehicles from other traffic zones towards zone i as a destination. The charging location shares (f_{home} , f_{work} , f_{POI}) represent the fraction of total energy demand that is expected to be charged at a particular type of location, and can be adjusted to capture different scenarios in terms of preferred charging locations.

For POIs, the estimation of charging needs follows a similar logic. However, since the mobility model does not specify how many vehicles stop at each POI, the charging demand is distributed proportionally to the number of POIs in each TZ. This approach ensures that zones with more POIs are allocated a larger share of the total POI-related charging demand. The distribution is given by:

$$E_{POI,i} = \left(f_{POI} \cdot C_{EV} \cdot \eta_{charge}^{-1} \cdot \sum_i VKM_{out,i} \right) \cdot \frac{m_i}{m_{tot}}, \quad (6)$$

where f_{POI} denotes the share of EVs charging at POIs, m_i is the number of POIs in zone i , and m_{tot} is the total number of POIs across all zones.

In Eqs. (4) and (5), the VKM is derived from the mobility demand model as follows:

$$VKM_{out,i} = 2 \cdot \sum_{j \neq i} p_{ij} \cdot n_i \cdot d_{ij}, \quad (7)$$

$$VKM_{in,i} = 2 \cdot \sum_{j \neq i} p_{ji} \cdot n_j \cdot d_{ij}, \quad (8)$$

where n_i is the number of EVs of traffic zone i , and d_{ij} is the distance between zones i and j . The factor of 2 accounts for round trips (outward and return trip to work).

3.2.2. Temporal demand

The temporal charging demand (i.e., the charging load profile) is determined by estimating the number of EVs charging on a given day and constructing the charging load profile for each individual vehicle. Both processes employ a stochastic modeling approach, ensuring that the charging load profile reflects behavioral heterogeneity and day-to-day variability. In this work, we assume an uncontrolled charging scheme, where vehicles begin charging immediately upon arrival at a constant power rate. However, the model is designed to be adaptable to controlled charging schemes, which will be explored in future investigations.

To estimate the number of EVs charging per day, we build on the experimentally validated model introduced by Pareschi et al. (2020), which introduces a threshold state of charge (SoC_0), below which vehicles are assumed to initiate charging. For each EV, this threshold is randomly assigned based on Pareschi's probabilistic distribution, which follows a normal distribution with a mean of 0.6 and a standard deviation of 0.2. Then, an average number of days between charging events (ΔN) is computed based on the daily state-of-charge depletion (ΔSoC_{daily}) of each EV

$$\Delta N = \max \left(1, \frac{1 - SoC_0}{\Delta SoC_{daily}} \right) \quad (9)$$

$$\Delta SoC_{daily} = \frac{E_{daily}}{0.8 \cdot Q} \quad (10)$$

Here, E_{daily} denotes the vehicle's daily energy demand in kWh, assigned randomly from the daily travel distance distribution of the TZ the vehicle belongs to, while Q represents the nominal battery capacity in kWh. The factor 0.8 accounts for the useful battery capacity for decision-making, in line with Pareschi's empirically calibrated model (Pareschi et al., 2020).

It is important to note that our approach slightly differs from the original model, as we directly assume ΔN for each EV, whereas Pareschi's work does not assume such a steady-state condition a priori. This assumption eliminates the need for multiple preliminary runs to reach model convergence. Once ΔN is determined, the model assigns a daily charging probability of $1/\Delta N$ to each vehicle and a random sampling process identifies whether a vehicle charges on a given day. This approach moves beyond simplistic assumptions (e.g., daily charging) by accommodating the behavior of vehicles with large battery capacities or low daily travel distances. For illustration, a plot of the daily charging probability as a function of the daily EV energy use for two battery capacities Q is provided in Appendix A.

For vehicles identified as charging on a given day, a 24-hour charging load profile is constructed by sampling several parameters based on the modeled scenario. Specifically, the charging location is assigned according to the distribution of home, work, and POIs charging shares. The arrival time ($t_{arrival}$ [h]) is sampled from the probability distribution of arrival times specific to the assigned charging location. The charging power (P_{charge} [kW]) is determined by the availability of chargers at the location and is capped by the vehicle's maximum charging power (P_{max} [kW]). Using these parameters, the charging load profile for a vehicle v , $P_{EV,v}(t)$ [kW], is defined as follows:

$$P_{EV,v}(t) = \begin{cases} P_{charge} & \text{if } t \in [t_{arrival}, t_{end}] \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

$$t_{end} = t_{arrival} + \frac{\Delta N \cdot E_{daily}}{\eta_{charge} \cdot P_{charge}} \quad (12)$$

Here, t_{end} denotes the end time of the charging session in h, which is calculated based on the charging duration while accounting for the charging efficiency η_{charge} .

3.3. EV-PV complementarity

The final step in the analysis evaluates the potential complementarity between PV energy and EVs, focusing primarily on the ability of locally installed PV systems to meet EV charging needs. This section comprises two components: the computation of time-dependent local PV production and the calculation of key indicators that quantify EV-PV complementarity.

3.3.1. PV production potential

The local PV production potential is calculated using the pvlib toolbox (Anderson et al., 2023), which enables detailed yet computationally efficient simulations by integrating environmental conditions, PV module specifications, and installation parameters. For environmental conditions, we use local weather data from the PVGIS-SARAH3 solar database, which can be directly extracted through pvlib (Jensen et al., 2023).

For each time step, the plane-of-array irradiance ($G_{POA}(t)$ [W/m²]) is calculated based on irradiance data and the PV module's installation angles (tilt and azimuth). These angles can be customized for fixed-tilt or tracking systems. The resulting irradiance is then used to determine the PV production $P_{PV}(t)$ [W], calculated using the so-called *PVWatts* model from pvlib to capture thermal losses, as shown hereafter

$$P_{PV}(t) = \eta_{PV} \cdot G_{POA}(t) \cdot [1 + \beta \cdot (T_{cell}(t) - T_{ref})] \quad (13)$$

with η_{PV} the nominal module efficiency, β the temperature coefficient in 1/°C, T_{cell} the solar cells operating temperature (calculated using the pre-implemented *PVsystem* model), and T_{ref} the reference temperature in °C (equal to 25 °C).

Angular losses are also automatically accounted for at each time step using the analytical model of Martin and Ruiz (2001). Additional system losses are added ex-post by an overall loss factor. This methodology includes all main loss mechanisms ensuring a robust assessment of the local PV production potential under real-world conditions.

3.3.2. EV-PV indicators

After estimating PV generation and EV charging demand, key indicators are used to assess their complementarity. These include self-sufficiency potential, self-consumption potential, and energy coverage (ratio of the total PV production to the EV charging demand over a given period).

In this work, we focus on the self-sufficiency potential (*SS*), which quantifies the proportion of the charging demand that can be met by PV production, assuming all available PV energy can be used for charging. It is calculated as the ratio of the coincident power (i.e., the overlap between PV generation and EV demand) to the total EV charging demand over a 24-hour period (Simoiu et al., 2021):

$$SS = \frac{\int \min[P_{PV}(t), P_{EV}(t)] dt}{\int P_{EV}(t) dt} \quad (14)$$

where $P_{EV}(t)$ is the aggregated charging demand for all EVs in W. This metric treats all PV generation and EV demand as part of a closed system, capturing the overall balance between PV production and EV charging demand.

Fig. 3. Map of Ethiopia (left) showing the administrative regions outlined in black according to the GADM dataset (Global Administrative Areas (GADM), 2024), with Addis Ababa highlighted in red. The study area of Addis Ababa (right) is also shown in greater detail with its administrative boundaries and traffic zones.

4. Case study

4.1. Study area

Fig. 3 illustrates the study area, defined by the administrative boundaries of Addis Ababa, which cover approximately 540 km² (Wubneh, 2013). These boundaries were obtained from the Global Administrative Areas (GADM) dataset (Global Administrative Areas (GADM), 2024). The area is divided into traffic zones measuring 1.95 km by 1.95 km, a grid resolution selected to effectively capture short-distance commuting patterns while ensuring manageable computational time.

Geospatial data, aggregated at the zone level, includes residential population figures from the GHS-POP dataset (Schiavina et al., 2023), along with the number of workplaces and points of interest obtained from OpenStreetMap (OpenStreetMap contributors, 2024). The workplaces and POIs are extracted to represent the majority of potential commuting destinations and charging locations (see the Appendix C). Notably, universities are also included as key destinations, reflecting their role in accommodating a non-negligible share of Addis Ababa's commuting population. The resulting dataset reveals 1,845 workplaces, and 3,633 POIs, alongside with a residential population of 5.54 million people.

4.2. Electric vehicle fleet

The simulated EV fleet consists of 100,000 vehicles, representing a realistic short-term projection in light of Ethiopia's expanding private vehicle market and the government's national target. As shown in Appendix B, even under conservative assumptions regarding the current EV stock, car renewal rates, and car ownership growth, this target could be achieved within approximately 3.6 years if all newly registered vehicles are EVs. The technical characteristics of the simulated EVs are summarized in Table 1. The fleet composition includes 80% battery electric vehicles (BEVs) and 20% plug-in hybrid electric vehicles (PHEVs), closely aligning with the distribution observed in 2023 African EV sales (International Energy Agency (IEA), 2024). Incorporating a share of PHEVs also reflects a realistic assumption regarding range anxiety faced by drivers due to Addis Ababa's emerging and limited charging infrastructure. Due to the lack of statistical data, battery capacities were selected based on those reported in the International Energy Agency (IEA) report (International Energy Agency (IEA), 2024) for a typical medium-sized passenger car. Specifically, we assume an average BEV battery capacity of 60 kWh, representative of mid-range passenger vehicles, and an average PHEV battery capacity of

15 kWh, sufficient to provide an electric range of approximately 60 km. Additionally, PHEVs are limited to a maximum charging power of 11 kW, which restricts their access to fast-charging stations. Although it varies by model, this limit is in line with the typical maximum charging power for PHEVs (Andrenacci et al., 2024).

4.3. Charging habits and infrastructure

4.3.1. Charging scenarios

In Addis Ababa, the future evolution of charging habits and the availability of charging infrastructure remain highly uncertain. In this context, a key question involves understanding how different charging locations might influence the spatial and temporal distribution of EV charging. This, in turn, affects the potential grid impacts and the charging infrastructure requirements, which are crucial factors for informing policy decisions and energy infrastructure planning. To explore this question, we analyze three archetypal charging scenarios, each representing distinct charging location patterns:

- **100% home:** This scenario assumes that all users charge their vehicles at home. It is typical for areas with accessible residential infrastructure and favorable overnight tariffs, reflecting standard overnight charging demand patterns.
- **100% work:** In this scenario, all charging takes place at work, reflecting the behavior of users who do not have access to home charging and rely entirely on employer-provided charging stations.
- **Mixed:** Charging is distributed across three locations (25% at home, 25% at workplaces, and 50% at public POIs such as shopping centers and leisure facilities). This scenario captures a more diverse set of charging behaviors and highlights the impact of a reliance on the public charging infrastructure.

Arrival times at the various charging locations are modeled using a normal distribution centered around typical arrival times. For home charging, the mean arrival time is assumed to be 6:00 PM, with a standard deviation of 2.7 h. For work charging, the mean arrival time is set at 9:00 AM, with a standard deviation of 1.8 h. In the absence of local data, these average arrival times are based on informed estimates from the authors who reside in Addis Ababa and are familiar with prevailing working hours. The standard deviations are taken from Swiss microcensus data (Federal Office for Spatial Development and Federal Statistical Office, 2021) as proxies. For charging at POIs, we assume that charging occurs randomly between the arrival time at work and the return home.

Table 1
Parameters of the simulated 100,000 EVs.

Parameter	BEV	PHEV	Reference
Share (%)	80	20	International Energy Agency (IEA) (2024)
Battery capacity (kWh)	60	15	International Energy Agency (IEA) (2024)
Energy consumption (kWh/km)	0.183	0.183	Fetene et al. (2017)
Maximum charging power (kW)	None	11	Own assumption

Table 2
Charger option availability at different locations.

Charger option	Home	Work	POIs
Level 1 - 3.2 kW	45%	–	–
Level 2 - 7.4 kW	40%	25%	15%
Level 2 - 11 kW	15%	50%	15%
Level 2 - 22 kW	–	25%	55%
Level 3 - 50 kW	–	–	15%

4.3.2. Charging infrastructure

Each charging location incorporates a diverse mix of power levels, informed by established proxy data (Table 2). Home charging primarily consists of slow (3.2 kW) and moderate (7.4 kW and 11 kW) chargers, following the distribution reported by Sorensen et al. (2023). POI charging is based on Swiss data for public charging infrastructure (Swiss Federal Office of Energy (SFOE), 2024). Notably, these charging power distributions align closely with data from other countries (Lucas et al., 2024; Brown et al., 2023), supporting the validity of the assumed charging power mix for this case study. Workplace charging is modeled with only level 2 chargers (Brown et al., 2023), with 11 kW units expected to dominate.

Following the approach of Lanz et al. (2022), fast charging is capped at 50 kW due to the limited availability of higher-power charging stations and the observation that, even for higher charging power levels, the average charging power typically remains below the nominal values. Additionally, a uniform charging efficiency of 90% is applied across all locations (Sears et al., 2014).

4.4. PV system

This study considers free-standing PV systems configured with an optimal tilt and azimuth angle, representative of typical installations in PV farms or standalone systems for solar-powered charging stations. Weather data for Addis Ababa was obtained for the year 2020. The PV system is modeled with a nominal module efficiency of 22%, reflecting the recent sales-weighted average for commercially available PV modules (Fraunhofer Institute for Solar Energy Systems, 2023). To account for real-world performance losses, a temperature coefficient of $-0.4\%/^{\circ}\text{C}$ (Haschke et al., 2017) and typical system losses of 14% were incorporated into the simulation. As a result, the model predicts an annual energy yield of 1,656.4 kWh/kWp, with the lowest energy generation observed during the rainy season, which occurs from July to September.

5. Results & discussion

5.1. Spatio-temporal charging demand

5.1.1. Spatial distribution

The total daily charging demand for 100,000 electric vehicles (EVs) is estimated at 353 MWh, based on an average daily commuting distance of 17.4 km per vehicle (see Appendix D for the distribution of travel distances derived from the mobility demand model). Although recent transport data for Addis Ababa is currently unavailable, this estimate aligns with commuting distances reported for cities of comparable size (Angel and Blei, 2016), and with an earlier study that found an average car commute of approximately 15 km in Addis Ababa (Bedelu

and de Langen, 2008). Given the city’s continued expansion, this small difference in travel distance is reasonable.

Examining the spatial distribution of the charging demand (Fig. 4) reveals variations in both the magnitude and the spatial pattern of the demand across the city. In the 100% work charging scenario, demand is highly concentrated in the city center, where most workplaces are located, with a per-zone demand peaking at 22.2 MWh. In contrast, the 100% home charging scenario shows a more dispersed pattern, with a maximum per-zone demand equal to 14.4 MWh. The mixed scenario presents an intermediate case, with a per-zone demand reaching 18.3 MWh. Notably, the spatial pattern in the mixed scenario closely resembles that of the 100% workplace scenario. This similarity arises because POIs are predominantly located near workplaces, leaving the 25% share of home charging to only slightly disperse the charging demand across traffic zones.

Building on this spatial distribution, Fig. 4.d also examines the per-zone charging demand as a function of the number of residents and workplaces for the 100% home charging and 100% workplace charging scenarios, respectively. In both cases, a positive correlation between the number of residents or workplaces and the charging demand per traffic zone is observed. However, the relationship does not follow a perfect linear trend. Notably, in the 100% home charging scenario, as the population within a traffic zone increases, the growth rate of the per-zone charging demand slightly diminishes. This non-linearity can be attributed to the fact that while the number of EVs scales proportionally with the population, the per-vehicle charging demand is higher in less densely populated zones as these zones tend to be located farther from workplaces. In contrast, in the 100% work charging scenario, the per-vehicle charging demand exhibits less sensitivity to the specific location of each traffic zone, primarily due to the more concentrated distribution of workplaces. This leads to a more linear trend between the number of workplaces and the charging demand per TZ. This linear trend is also driven by the underlying fact that, in Addis Ababa, the number of EVs scales linearly with the number of workplaces. These results underscore the importance of our spatially explicit approach to accurately capture the complex dependencies of the charging demand on the urban spatial structure.

5.1.2. Temporal distribution

The charging scenario strongly shapes the EV charging load profile, influencing both the timing and intensity of demand peaks, as illustrated in Fig. 5. Home charging induces a pronounced evening peak of 46.6 ± 0.3 MW, coinciding with the typical peak grid hours. In contrast, workplace charging shifts this peak to the late morning, avoiding overlap with the evening grid peak. However, the peak intensity for workplace charging is higher, reaching 74.8 ± 0.5 MW. This is due to the lower dispersion in arrival times and the higher charging power levels at workplaces compared to home charging. This suggests that a 100% workplace charging strategy could also impose important stress on the grid, particularly under the assumption of uncontrolled charging adopted in this study. The mixed charging scenario presents a more balanced charging load profile. The charging demand is distributed more evenly throughout the day, with a peak in the morning reaching only 33.2 ± 0.6 MW. This result underscores the potential benefits of charging a portion of the fleet at POIs, which creates a smoother demand profile and reduces the overlap of charging events with peak grid hours.

Fig. 4. Map of the daily per-zone charging demand for the three charging scenarios: (a) 100% home charging, (b) 100% work charging, and (c) mixed charging. The traffic zone size is 1.95 km by 1.95 km. Panel (d) shows the per-zone charging demand as a function of the (normalized) number of residents and workplaces.

Since all EVs do not charge simultaneously, it is also interesting to note that the average peak demand per vehicle remains consistently lower than the average available charging power. Given that only about one-third of the 100,000 EVs charge daily, the peak demand for home charging is just 1.4 kW per charging EV, despite an average home charging power of approximately 6.0 kW. This value aligns with previous studies (Pareschi et al., 2020) and results from the dispersion in vehicle arrival times and the relatively low per-vehicle charging demand, which limits the number of EVs charging at the same time. At workplaces, the peak demand per charging EV is higher (around 2.3 kW) but remains well below the average workplace charging power of approximately 12.8 kW.

5.2. Implications on the required number of charging points

The developed model also enables the estimation of charging infrastructure requirements, particularly the number of charging points needed. Here, charging points are defined as the total number of sockets required for electric vehicles to recharge (Gnann et al., 2018). To determine the number of charging points, we apply the concept of a charging point-to-EV ratio, which expresses how many charging points are needed relative to the number of EVs expected at a given location. This ratio varies according to usage patterns: for example, residential charging typically assumes a low ratio, as most vehicles are expected to

Table 3

Charging points per EV and the total required number of charging points in three different charging scenarios at various locations. The values are derived from the average charging point-to-EV ratio obtained over 10 model runs.

Charging location	Home	Work	POIs
Charging point-to-EV ratio	1.0	0.34	0.03
Required charging points:			
100% home	100,000	–	–
100% work	–	32,000	–
Mixed	25,000	8000	1500

have access to a dedicated charging point, whereas public fast-charging stations operate at considerably lower ratios because a smaller number of points can be shared by multiple vehicles over time. Table 3 provides estimates of the charging point-to-EV ratios, as well as the total number of charging points per location under the three charging scenarios.

In residential settings, it is likely that each electric vehicle will be equipped with a dedicated charging point, as privately owned charging infrastructure is rarely shared. While this arrangement offers convenience for EV users, it is inefficient from an infrastructure perspective. Hence, in the 100% home charging scenario, such a setup would require 100,000 charging points. Each of these would likely need to

Fig. 5. EV charging load profiles for the three charging scenarios, aggregated across all TZs and electric vehicles. Each scenario is simulated five times to assess the impact of day-to-day variability. The average arrival times at work (vertical blue dashed line) and at home (vertical purple dashed line) are also shown alongside the typical peak grid hours in Addis Ababa.

be paired with either a dedicated charging station or, at a minimum, a reinforced charging socket.

At workplaces, the charging point-to-EV ratio is approximately three times lower than in residential settings. This outcome emerges from our charging-decision model, which shows that only a fraction of the EV fleet requires charging on any given day, thereby leading to a lower ratio. Our findings are consistent with the literature, with a recent review by Xylia et al. (2025) reporting an average ratio of 0.5 for private passenger vehicle charging, encompassing both home and workplace location. As emphasized by the authors, no ratio dedicated to workplaces alone is available in the existing literature, which limits direct comparison and highlights the contribution of our simulation in providing such a location-specific estimate. It is also important to note that the charging point-to-EV ratio is influenced by both daily charging demand and the battery capacities of the vehicles, making it highly context-dependent. In the case of Addis Ababa, if battery capacities continue to increase in line with global trends, the current estimated ratio is expected to decline further.

At POIs, the estimated charging point-to-EV ratio is ten times lower than at workplaces, making it the most efficient locations for minimizing the required number of charging points. This value is derived from the minimum number of EVs charging simultaneously, which remains low due to the combination of high charging powers and dispersed arrival times at points of interest. While this reflects a best-case scenario with no idle time (i.e., users release their chargers immediately after their sessions), such an assumption is reasonable for fast charging, where idle times are typically short (Borlaug et al., 2023; Zhao et al., 2025), and can be further reduced through mechanisms such as idle fees. Similar to workplace charging, a direct comparison with the literature is difficult, as studies reporting charging point-to-EV ratios are conducted in varying contexts and with different technological scopes. Overall, our estimate is broadly in line with the literature, which reports an average ratio of approximately 0.01 (Xylia et al., 2025), with our model providing a context-specific figure.

5.3. Potential for PV-based EV charging

Leveraging PV energy for EV charging in regions with abundant solar resources, such as Addis Ababa, offers a promising opportunity

to reduce the grid electricity demand for charging while aligning with broader goals of decarbonization. The self-sufficiency potential, as defined in Section 3, is depicted in Fig. 6, which presents a box plot of the self-sufficiency potential calculated for all weekdays over a year. The analysis considers the three charging scenarios and various levels of PV capacity, ranging from 0.5 kW_p/EV to 2.0 kW_p/EV, approximately equivalent to one to four modern silicon solar panels per EV. In Addis Ababa, this range produces between 2.3 kWh (0.5 kW_p/EV) and 9.1 kWh (2.0 kW_p/EV) of PV energy per EV per day on average.

Despite daily and scenario-specific variations, a key finding is that an important share of the charging demand can reliably be met by PV energy. Even in the 100% home charging scenario (where temporal complementarity between PV production and EV charging is poor due to predominantly nighttime charging), the average self-sufficiency potential ranges from 16.0% (0.5 kW_p/EV) to 26.5% (2.0 kW_p/EV). The 100% work charging scenario demonstrates substantially higher potential, with averages ranging from 43.1% to 84.9%. The mixed charging scenario achieves intermediate levels, with an average self-sufficiency potential ranging from 56.6% to 73.9%.

Notably, in the 100% work charging scenario, self-sufficiency levels exceeding 95% are achieved on several days for PV capacities of 1.0 kW_p/EV or higher, owing to the strong temporal alignment between PV generation and EV charging needs. Conversely, the mixed charging scenario includes some evening and nighttime charging, reducing its temporal alignment with PV production. However, this scenario exhibits less day-to-day variability, as the broad charging load profile ensures that part of the available solar energy is always used for EV charging. As shown in Fig. 6, self-sufficiency also begins to plateau beyond 1.5 kW_p/EV. Above this threshold, additional PV production results in surplus solar energy that cannot be used for charging, thereby saturating the self-sufficiency potential. This suggests that beyond approximately 1.5 kW_p/EV, investing in additional PV capacity yields only marginal benefits for direct EV charging and may only be relevant if surplus energy can be used for other purposes (e.g., grid export or battery storage).

A closer examination of monthly variations further highlights the differences across charging scenarios, as illustrated in Fig. 7.a. As anticipated, the 100% work charging scenario achieves higher average self-sufficiency levels compared to the mixed charging scenario in most months. However, it also exhibits greater variability, with larger day-to-day variations and more pronounced month-to-month fluctuations in the average values. Specifically, the average self-sufficiency in the 100% work charging scenario ranges from 54% to 94%, with the lowest levels occurring during July and August, coinciding with the rainy season. In contrast, the mixed charging scenario offers a more stable self-sufficiency range of 64% to 76%. The attenuated complementarity between PV generation and work charging during the rainy season can be attributed to limited PV production on some mornings. This seasonal mismatch is further illustrated in the weekly PV production curves for January and July (Fig. 7.b), which underscore the advantages of charging at POIs to mitigate the effects of weather variability during the rainy season.

5.4. Discussion

The results indicate that the introduction of 100,000 EVs in Addis Ababa would lead to an additional daily demand of 353 MWh for EV charging. Relative to the city's current electricity demand profile, this corresponds to an approximate 1.5% rise in the overall daily electricity demand. While this increase appears manageable and suggests that the deployment of the first wave of EVs could proceed without major challenges, it nonetheless requires proper planning, as the additional demand is not negligible. Addis Ababa's electricity grid already operates near full capacity, and frequent power interruptions observed in many areas (Tsegai, 2022; Meles, 2020). The spatial analysis shows that the concentrated charging demand could further strain specific parts

Fig. 6. Self-sufficiency potential as a function of the installed nominal PV capacity per EV for the different charging scenarios. Boxplots are based on the daily self-sufficiency potential for all 262 weekdays of the year 2020. The boxplots represent the daily self-sufficiency potential for all 262 weekdays of 2020. They show the averages (square markers), medians (horizontal lines), interquartile ranges (IQR, box outlines), and outliers (black dots). The whiskers extend from the hinge to the highest and lowest values within $1.5 \times \text{IQR}$. Nominal PV capacities range from 0.5 to 2.0 kW_p/EV, corresponding to surface areas of approximately 2.3 to 9.0 m²/EV.

Fig. 7. Influence of monthly variations on the self-sufficiency potential: (a) radar plot of the monthly self-sufficiency potential (average and standard deviation) for the three charging scenarios, based on a PV capacity of 1.5 kW_p/EV; (b) Hourly PV production profiles for a representative week in January and July.

of the grid. Furthermore, this 1.5% increase does not account for the electrification of public transport, nor does it consider the potential for private vehicle ownership to exceed 100,000 EVs, which would amplify the charging demand. This analysis provides a foundation for supporting future EV adoption by offering scalable estimates and identifying high-demand charging locations.

The charging location plays an important role in shaping the temporal distribution of the charging demand. Home charging is likely to coincide with existing evening peak hours, while workplace charging could introduce a new peak of 74.8 MW in the morning, contrasting with the current electricity demand profile (see Fig. 1). However, this additional load should be manageable, as it represents less than 6% of the current peak demand and would occur outside the existing peak hours. It is important to emphasize that, under our hypothesis, the EV charging load profiles presented here represent the most probable scenario. However, statistical fluctuations in arrival times could lead

to higher peak demands on certain days. In the worst-case scenario (where all vehicles charging on a given day charge simultaneously), peak demand could increase by approximately 193 MW in the 100% home charging scenario and 410 MW in the 100% work charging scenario, corresponding to 14.7% and 31.3% increases in the current peak demand, respectively. Although such scenarios are unlikely, they underscore the need for a robust electricity grid to accommodate potential extreme cases. Demand-side strategies such as implementing smart charging systems or promoting the use of public charging stations could mitigate the risk of extreme peak demands by shifting and spreading the load more evenly throughout the day, thereby reducing the need for costly grid upgrades. Notably, existing evidence suggests that public charging stations tend to be used when available, even if other charging options are accessible (Liu et al., 2022).

Charging at POIs could also substantially reduce the number of required charging stations. This reduction arises not only from the

Fig. 8. Dependence of EV charging peak load (red, left axis) and the percentage of EVs charging simultaneously (blue, right axis) on the charging power. Error bars represent daily variability in EV load profiles. Results are derived from a dummy scenario with a single charging power level and a tight distribution in arrival times (standard deviation equal to 1.8 h), representing a highly sensitive case.

assumed ideal charging behavior but also from the greater share of fast chargers typically installed at POIs. However, the integration of fast chargers introduces a potential trade-off: while reducing the number of charging points improves cost efficiency and profitability for charge point operators by maximizing energy throughput per station, it may also lead to an increase in peak power demand. Interestingly, as shown in Fig. 8, peak power demand rises with a charging power only up to approximately 20 kW, beyond which it stabilizes and becomes relatively independent of further increases in charging power. This behavior is driven by the interplay between charging power and the maximum number of EVs charging simultaneously, the latter decreasing as charging power increases. This finding suggests that deploying fast chargers at locations requiring high charging powers (e.g., above 22 kW), such as POIs with short dwell times like shopping centers, does not exacerbate peak power demand, challenging the assumption that high-power charging strains the grid. Instead, fast chargers can optimize charging station usage while maintaining a manageable peak load.

PV-based charging has significant potential to meet a large share of the EV charging demand, particularly at workplaces and POIs. However, our analysis indicates that beyond a PV capacity of 1.5 kW_p/EV, additional PV capacity yields only marginal gains in self-sufficiency. This limitation arises from the inherent mismatch between PV generation and EV charging demand, which persists across our three archetypal scenarios. Indeed, on average, daily solar energy generation exceeds daily EV charging demand at 1.0 kW_p/EV and above. Nonetheless, more advanced charging scenarios or strategies could improve PV self-sufficiency. In particular, smart charging approaches such as dynamic scheduling and demand-responsive charging could help shift charging times to better coincide with peak solar production hours.

6. Conclusion

Transport electrification is gaining momentum in Africa, offering a key opportunity to cut greenhouse gas emissions and reduce dependence on imported fossil fuels when paired with renewable energy. However, many African regions lack comprehensive transport and energy data, posing a significant barrier to electric mobility planning. This article introduces a novel modeling framework specifically designed

for regions with limited data availability. The framework enables the simulation of mobility patterns, spatio-temporal charging needs, and the complementarity between EVs and PV energy by leveraging open-source geospatial data. Additionally, it facilitates scenario-based analyses, providing actionable insights for policymakers and energy planners to guide energy infrastructure development.

The framework is applied to Addis Ababa, simulating 100,000 EVs and demonstrating how one of Africa's largest cities could meet a substantial share of its private passenger transport energy demand with locally generated PV energy. The analysis considers three distinct charging scenarios: home charging, workplace charging, and a mixed scenario where 50% of charging occurs at POIs. Based on the results, the following key findings can be drawn:

1. While the per-vehicle charging demand is relatively low (3.53 kWh) due to short daily commuting distances, the total demand for 100,000 EVs results in a 1.5% increase in overall daily electricity consumption.
2. The charging scenario significantly affects the spatial charging demand distribution. Workplace and POI charging concentrates the charging demand in the city center, whereas home charging shifts it to residential areas and disperses slightly the demand.
3. The charging scenarios also shape the charging load profile. Home charging leads to an evening peak aligned with current electricity peak hours, while workplace charging generates an earlier but higher peak. Charging at POIs leads to a more evenly distributed load, highlighting the benefit of charging at public places.
4. The number of required charging points varies by location. Workplace charging requires about one charger per three EVs, unlike home charging, where each EV has a dedicated unit. At POIs, fast chargers and dispersed arrivals further reduce charging points by a factor of ten.
5. Workplace and POI charging align well with PV production. The average daily self-sufficiency potential exceeds 80% at workplaces and 70% in the mixed charging scenario for PV capacities of 1.5 kW_p/EV or above. While the mixed charging scenario exhibits slightly lower self-sufficiency, it shows less variability, particularly during the rainy season.

We acknowledge several limitations in our study. While the results for Addis Ababa were compared with existing literature where possible, some were derived using proxy data (e.g., charging power distribution) or informed assumptions (e.g., average arrival times at home and work). One limitation of this study is the lack of real-world data specific to Addis Ababa, particularly for the charging demand modeling step, which required the use of some informed assumptions. Should more data become available, the model could be further refined to incorporate local specificities, such as the detailed distribution of arrival times or the characteristics of the EV fleet. In addition, incorporating more detailed geospatial data, including local motorization rates, could further enhance the allocation of EVs across traffic zones. Regarding the assessment of EV–PV complementarity, our analysis is limited to the year 2020. Extending the study to assess multiple years would provide a more comprehensive evaluation. However, this limitation is unlikely to significantly impact the results, given that annual solar irradiance variations are minimal (data from PVGIS-SARAH3 indicate fluctuations of about 2% per year in Addis Ababa).

For future research, our model could be applied to other African cities with diverse vehicle types, such as motorbikes, or different urban structures, including those with multiple business districts. Expanding the model to capture a broader scope of mobility demand would also be valuable, provided that relevant data becomes available. For instance, considering mobility associated with shopping or entertainment is expected to slightly increase the daily travel distance, as these activities often involve additional trips beyond commuting. This

also includes accounting for weekend mobility demand and charging behavior, as weekend mobility patterns differ significantly from those on weekdays. Notably, home charging during weekends could better align with residential PV generation, enhancing the self-sufficiency of this charging location. Additionally, considering alternative weekday mobility patterns, such as commuting to park-and-ride facilities, could offer valuable insights into the long-term development pathways of the overall passenger transport system, integrating both public and private mobility. Further analysis could also explore the impact of smart charging strategies on charging load profiles and EV-PV complementarity, providing insights into mitigating grid strain while maximizing solar energy use. Expanding the model to individual charging stations with techno-economic analyses could further refine these insights, offering more detailed and practical guidance for PV-based charging stations. In this context, pairing PV with stationary batteries could also be a cost-effective strategy to investigate, especially given the rapidly declining costs of battery storage.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Jérémy Dumoulin: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Software, Methodology, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Dawit Habtu Gebremeskel:** Writing – original draft, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Kanchwodia Gashaw:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Ingeborg Graabak:** Writing – original draft, Conceptualization. **Noémie Jeannin:** Writing – review & editing. **Alejandro Pena-Bello:** Writing – review & editing. **Christophe Ballif:** Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition. **Nicolas Wyrtsch:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of Generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work, the authors used GPT-3.5 Language Model to enhance its quality and clarity. After using this tool, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the publication.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Charging probability function

See Fig. A.1.

Fig. A.1. Charging probability function as a function of daily EV energy use, for two battery capacities. The plot displays the average charging probability (solid line) along with the standard deviation. Results are derived from random sampling of 50,000 values.

Appendix B. EV fleet share dynamics

Considering a fixed stock of vehicles (electric and non-electric), the evolution of the EV fleet share can be modeled considering the balance between the vehicle fleet renewal rate (assumed to occur at the same rate across all vehicle types) and the introduction of new EVs

$$\frac{ds}{dt} = \lambda(\sigma - s(t)) \tag{B.1}$$

where $s(t)$ represents the EV share in the fleet at time t , λ is the fleet renewal rate (the average share of vehicles replaced per unit time), and σ denotes the EV share in new vehicle registrations.

Solving this equation with the initial condition $s(0) = s_0$ gives:

$$s(t) = \sigma + (s_0 - \sigma)exp(-\lambda t) \tag{B.2}$$

which describes a growing function converging towards the EV share in new vehicle registrations σ , with a characteristic time scale of $1/\lambda$.

The numerical results, assuming an average vehicle lifetime of 20 years ($\lambda = 1/20$) and $s_0 = 0$, indicate that the transition towards an EV-dominated fleet is strongly influenced by the EV share in new registrations (σ) and, consequently, the effectiveness of EV adoption policies. If all newly registered vehicles are EVs ($\sigma = 1$), reaching 100,000 EVs (approximately 1/6 of the current vehicle stock in Addis Ababa) would take just 3.6 years. For $\sigma = 0.5$, the time required is around 8.1 years. However, for $\sigma = 0.2$, the time extends significantly to 35.8 years.

Appendix C. OSM query for workplace and POI extraction

Workplaces

```
tags = {
  "building": ["industrial", "office"],
  "company": True,
  "landuse": ["industrial", "commercial", "retail"],
  "industrial": True,
  "office": True,
  "amenity": [
    "university", "research_institute",
```

```

    "hospital", "townhall",
    "conference_centre", "factory",
    "corporate_office", "government",
    "bank", "police",
    "fire_station", "post_office",
    "call_centre", "logistics_centre"
  ]
}

Points of interest

tags = {
  "amenity": [
    "fuel", "parking",
    "parking_entrance", "bicycle_parking",
    "college", "university",
    "school", "kindergarten",
    "library", "music_school",
    "language_school", "clinic",
    "dentist", "doctors",
    "hospital", "pharmacy",
    "veterinary",
    "cafe", "ice_cream",
    "internet_cafe", "restaurant",
    "fast_food", "bar",
    "pub", "biergarten",
    "theatre", "cinema",
    "music_venue", "nightclub",
    "casino", "gambling",
    "stripclub", "arts_centre",
    "community_centre", "social_centre",
    "exhibition_centre", "attraction",
    "viewpoint", "aquarium",
    "beach_resort", "gallery",
    "museum", "theme_park",
    "zoo", "artwork"
  ],
  "shop": [
    "supermarket", "mall",
    "department_store", "convenience"
  ],
  "tourism": [
    "hotel", "guest_house",
    "hostel", "motel",
    "camp_site", "apartment"
  ],
  "leisure": [
    "stadium", "sports_centre",
    "swimming_pool", "fitness_centre"
  ]
}

```

Appendix D. Daily commuting distance distribution

See Fig. D.1.

Appendix E. Electricity demand profile for Addis Ababa

Hosting 30% of the urban population of Ethiopia, Addis Ababa, the capital of Ethiopia and the country’s political and economic center, the seat of head offices of African Union & UN Economic commission for Africa, home to several small to high-scale industries, is one of the fastest growing cities on the continent. Its geographic location in the center of Ethiopia, combined with lack of development in other urban centers have given the capital the majority of social and economic

Fig. D.1. Histogram of the daily commuting distance (two-way) for the 100,000 simulated EVs.

infrastructure in the country. This makes Addis Ababa the largest electric load center in the country.

Due to the absence of a specific load curve for the study area (Addis Ababa administrative region), the national load curve for 2024, which has a peak demand of 4,560 MW, was scaled to match the peak demand of Addis Ababa. The peak demand for Addis Ababa was estimated based on the extended Addis Ababa region’s 2024 peak demand of 2,100 MW (Japan International Cooperation Agency, 2017), adjusted proportionally to the population within the study area. The study area comprises 5.54 million people, while a GIS analysis indicates that the extended region encompasses 8.88 million inhabitants. As a result, the study area represents 28.7% of the national demand, with an estimated peak intensity of 1,310 MW and a total daily energy demand of 23,198 MWh.

Data availability

The current version of the open-source modeling framework is publicly accessible on GitHub (<https://github.com/evpv-simulator>). Additionally, the specific version of the code, along with all data used in this work is available on Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14826594>), ensuring the complete reproducibility of our analyses.

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